

FORMATION OF VERBAL ASSOCIATIONS IN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: This article deals with condition, characteristic features, connections of verbal associations in linguistics. In addition, its main peculiarities, its importance, in linguistics and functional features of verbal associations are highlighted in the article.

As a result of investigation the following results were obtained: a) creation and significance of verbal association, particularly their steps in mind has been scientifically proved; b) the possibility of verbal associations to present the thoughts of the people, cultural and world outlook has been verified; c) types of verbal associations has been verified;

Key words: verbal associations, written texts, literary language, speech culture, social phenomenon, communication, socio-cultural aspect, direct forming associations, indirect forming associations.

Introduction. Verbal associations are specific occurrence in linguistics. It is natural that, this linguistic phenomenon, that is, the verbal association, is an integral part of the existence of any human mind, an important factor of human development, as well as one the forms of preserving the experiences of the psychology. In addition, the verbal associations have been characterized as a cultural relic of the people, both spiritual and cultural value, in terms of its relative stability.

Research methods. Interest to verbal associations has grown significantly in recent years and many modern members of society, regardless of nationality and profession. Ancient written texts, which can be called a monument to human culture, significantly determine the worldview and perception of the world, the value system and the image of the universe of all peoples. Associations of written texts contain information about year of human experience and therefore, they are Valuable source of knowledge about people's life, tradition and culture. Verbal associations have always been the object of written text of research various field of human knowledge, including philosophers, linguistics, psychologists, cultural scientists emphasize the concept of association, (Nurmonova, Iskandarova, Lutfullayeva) moreover a special type of text is currently distinguished in linguistics.

Results and discussions. Associations are also noted as a special type of text that reflects tradition as well as the living spiritual culture of the people. It is impossible to create verbal associations without language of humanity. This type of association is considered by cultural and educational aspect.

Verbal associations reflects the spiritual manifestations of certain religion, tradition are transmitted from ancestor to generations with written examples.

Another feature of special text is its lexical composition. The lexical units of each language are unique, the content of vocabulary is defined by the limitation of the functions and the level of application of the mass can be separated with that item.[1]

The area of distribution in general consumption, the scope of use by people's activities, constitutes an unlimited lexicon of the language dictionary. A lexicon with a limited scope is spread among people united by a certain place or profession, social characteristics and common interests[2].

According to the linguist A.V. Ivanov, the lexicon in a special text is divided into several types, such as a special lexicon, a scientific lexicon, a lexicon for general use, in a certain sense, the movement of the lexicon, the processes of its enrichment with new units, as well as the possibility of functioning in different layers of the lexical structure of the language. because of the multiple meanings of the word creator[3].

Linguist D.S. Likhachev writes that the word has disappeared along with the phenomenon it expresses, and believes that compassion or kindness is absent in language because it does not exist in life [6].

One of the main characteristics of a literary language is that any developed language shows forms that can serve in any field of human activity. Without this possibility, the communication of its owners in any language will be limited [9].

It seems that the expressiveness and richness of the speaker's language in the association and a connection is observed between the ability to find a way into the hearts of listeners[12]. Adherence to the norms of literary language indicates the speech culture of the speaker. At the same time, using lexical and stylistic tools, bright and figurative speech is created. Meeting such requirements is important in the development of the speaker's individual style.

The use of words and phrases in the oral style of speech should not go beyond the limits of literary language and language norms[11]. On the contrary, spoken language should convey to the listener a connection to the spoken word.

According to Krushevskiy verbal associations are divided into two groups: a) direct forming associations, b) indirect forming associations.[5]

Professor Nurmonov manifested complexing the ideas of F.de.Sossyur about associative communication in his work. In addition, he identified distinction between associative and syntagmatic communication.[8]

Russian psychologist A.R.Luriya classified two types of verbal associations from the point of infant's communication.[7] M.M.Pokrovskiy agreed her idea.[10]

In the recent years, it is paid attention more to verbal associations, connection between stimulated word and association in linguistics.

For instance, L.E. Kuztensova studied associations related to the concept of love, divided into paradigmatic and syntagmatic types according to the nature of the relationship between the stimulus word and the associate.

In accordance with his conception, the first type of association helps to determine paradigmatic lines in humans' mind, while the second type of associations informs combinability of lexis terms, stimulus word, characteristics of phrases in discourse.[4]

Conclusion. It can be concluded that verbal associations can be made differently in human's speech and mind.

Verbal association is one of the permanent issues of social research that meets the essence of human needs in all aspects and spheres of human, group, and social life. This phenomenon, which includes such qualities as nobility, loyalty, good morals, strength, selflessness, is a problem that has attracted sages and thinkers of different times and cultures since ancient times.

Associations as a social phenomenon has been studied in various subjects of social and humanitarian knowledge, in particular, by such disciplines as psychology, sociology, social and cultural anthropology. For example, the use of the modern Uzbek language in the world community, as well as in Uzbekistan, the socio-cultural, it is known that it undergoes changes under the influence of political processes.

Over the years, the spiritual values and cultural traditions that were under the pressure of the historical period began to develop again in the society.

As a result of our research, we can form the following conclusions:

verbal associations, in particular, the result of human's thinking ability;
creation of verbal associations is differently according to the following aspects:
culture, tradition, age, sex, occupation, background knowledge and etc.

c) types of verbal associations are differently in theory. But more consistences were given above.

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